

FUNCTIONAL RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN LEAVES AND STEM ACROSS CANOPY LAYERS IN TWO CONTRASTING CLONES OF *POPULUS NIGRA* L.

Russo, G.¹, Beritognolo, I.¹, Sabatti, M.², Climent, J.M.³, Lauteri, M.¹, De Angelis, P.²

Affiliations

¹*Institute of Research on Terrestrial Ecosystems (IRET), National Research Council (CNR), Porano, Italy*

²*Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-food and Forest systems (DIBAF), University of Tuscia, Viterbo, Italy*

³*Departamento de Ecología y Genética Forestal, Centro de Investigación Forestal Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (INIA-CIFOR), Madrid, Spain*

Corresponding author: Giuseppe Russo; e-mail: giuseppe.russo@ibaf.cnr.it

Keywords

Black poplar, canopy effect, carbon stable isotopes, source-sink relationships

Abstract

Populus nigra L. represents a model system for plant biology and has a productive interest in breeding for short rotation forestry. The growth potential and adaptive capacity of this species are well characterized, but the canopy effect is poorly investigated. We analyzed morphological and functional leaf traits across a multilayer canopy profile in two contrasting clones of this species, 58-861 and Poli, respectively from northern and southern Italy, grown in field plantation. The results revealed how the variation of leaf functional traits was structured within the canopy. The two clones showed differences in leaf morphology and water use efficiency, but organized a similar functional canopy structure along a vertical profile, related to a gradient of light radiation. An acropetal enrichment gradient of carbon stable isotope was found both in leaves and stem wood across a vertical canopy profile and a tight correlation was found between carbon stable isotopes of leaves and of the respective stem section. Such a functional relationship indicates that substrates for stem growth were sourced from leaf assimilates of the closest canopy layer. These results characterize the physiology of black poplar under micro-environmental conditions at intra-canopy scale and contribute to clarify the canopy effect in young trees.

1. Introduction

Poplars (*Populus* spp.) represent a model system for research on trees and offer many features, such as wood formation, seasonality and adaptive traits, which are not easily addressed in herbaceous models, as *Arabidopsis* and rice (Jansson and Douglas, 2007). *Populus* species with wide geographic range display a large functional adaptation to diverse environments (Soolanayakanahally et al., 2015). The large genetic and phenotypic variation found within and among populations suggests a large adaptive potential in the riparian species *Populus nigra* L. (Chamaillard et al., 2011; Smulders et al., 2008). This ability has both an ecological and productive interest to attain high yield of biomass and wood, but, still little information exists on ecological sensitivity, reaction norms and phenotypic plasticity of poplar clones (Pliura et al., 2014). Studies that compare contrasting clones in common garden are an efficient strategy to investigate the environmental adaptation of plants. Two *P. nigra* clones, Poli and 58-861, respectively from contrasting environments of South and North of Italy, were previously compared and showed adaptive differences related to abiotic stress response (Gaudet et al., 2011; Iori et al., 2016; Marmioli et al., 2013; Zacchini et al. 2009). Studies on the response to drought in these clones found differences in leaf functional traits and leaf morphology. Functional markers were utilized to characterize their ecophysiological behaviour, among which the Instantaneous Water Use Efficiency (W_t), expressed as the ratio assimilation/transpiration and the carbon isotopic composition of foliage ($\delta^{13}C$), which is a proxy of intrinsic water use efficiency (Farquhar et al. 1989; Perez et al., 2013; Seibt et al., 2008). Both W_t and leaf $\delta^{13}C$ have indicated that clone 58-861 uses water with greater efficiency and strongly reduces stomatal conductance in response to drought. On the opposite, clone Poli reacts to drought with slight stomatal regulation but expresses a better capacity to withstand drought-induced oxidative stress (Cocozza et al., 2010; Regier et al. 2009). Overall, these studies have characterized clone Poli as “drought tolerant” and clone 58-861 as “drought sensitive“.

The interactions between leaf traits and the corresponding canopy section along the vertical profile are related to the canopy effect and provide knowledge about the whole plant system. The vertical profile of carbon allocation is highly relevant, because leaves

across canopy layers are exposed to different micro-environmental conditions and contribute to canopy photosynthesis as integrated effect of carbon gains (Niinemets, 2014). Several studies investigated the canopy effect on mature forest trees. The analysis of leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from bottom to top canopy revealed a gradient of acropetal isotopic enrichment. Significant effects of canopy profiles were also observed on leaf physiology, photosynthetic capacity and light energy dissipation (Van der Merwe and Medina, 1991; Scartazza et al., 2016). The canopy effect is poorly investigated in open-field plantations and it is not clear whether the vertical profile observed in mature and aged trees also occurs in relatively young and short height trees. The aim of this study was to investigate the canopy effect in an open field plantation by exploring the patterns of leaf functional traits across canopy layers and testing functional relationships between leaf traits and stem. The study was conducted on two divergent *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden plantation. The analysis of leaf morphology, gas exchanges and stable carbon isotopes of leaves and stem confirmed the divergent ecophysiological behavior of these clones but also revealed common intra-canopy patterns. Robust functional relationships between $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of leaves and stem clarify the source-sink transport across canopy layers and indicate the source of substrate used for stem growth. The analysis of canopy profiles improves our understanding of growth of the whole plant in the juvenile phase of *P. nigra*.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Plant material and growth conditions

The experiment was conducted on clonal rooted cuttings obtained from two *P. nigra* genotypes sampled from natural populations. The first genotype, named 58-861, is a female plant from Val Cenischia (Torino province, Northern Italy, latitude 45° 09'N, longitude 07°01'E, altitude 597 m a.s.l.; seasonal mean rainfall 315 mm; seasonal average temperature 25.7°C) near Dora Riparia and close to Alps mountains. The second genotype, named Poli, is a male plant from Policoro (Matera province, Southern Italy, latitude 40° 09'N, longitude 16° 41'E, Altitude. 7 m a.s.l.; seasonal mean rainfall 116 mm; seasonal average temperature 29.3°C) near Sinni river and close to Ionio Sea. During April 2008, 10 homogeneous 25 cm-long woody cuttings of each genotype were randomly planted, in an open field at the farm of the University of Tuscia (Viterbo,

Italy, latitude 42° 25' N, longitude 12° 05' E; altitude 309 m a.s.l.; seasonal mean rainfall 268 mm; seasonal average temperature 23.3°C), with a spacing of 2 by 0.75 m. The soil of the experimental field had a sandy loam soil texture (sand 57.5%, silt 34.6% and clay 7.9%) and pH 7.1. In January 2009, after the first season of growth, the plants were pruned to obtain single stem trees. The experimental analyses were carried from June to September 2009. During this period, the average daily temperature was 23.01°C and seasonal rainfall was 93.40 mm. The plantation was regularly irrigated after planting, and weed control was carried out throughout the growing season to obtain an optimal establishment. The plantation was set up and managed as a standard poplar plantation in order to observe plants in real field conditions. The average plant height, measured at the end of season, was 353±13.5 cm in Poli and 459±31.1 cm in 58-861. In order to study leaf traits across a vertical profile, the plant height of each clone was virtually divided in three vertical canopy layers of equal size, here called layer 1 (top), layer 2 (middle) and layer 3 (bottom).

2.2 Leaf morphology and gas exchange

We analyzed mature leaves from the middle part of each canopy layer during the entire growing season (June – September) in intervals of 30 days. Each sample or measurement included 10 leaves (each one from a plant replicate) per clone and per layer. The photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) on the sampled leaves of each canopy layer was measured by an instrument Li-250A Light Meter (LI-COR inc., Nebraska U.S.A.), avoiding cloudy conditions (Tab. 1). The leaf gas exchange analyses were performed on leaves in the field with a LiCor 6400 instrument (LI-COR inc., Nebraska U.S.A.), with PAR set to match the intensity experimentally measured in the respective canopy layer of each leaf and [CO₂] concentration set at 380 ppm. The average Vapor-pressure deficit (VPD) of leaf was 1.15±0.08 kPa and average air temperature (T_{air}) was 25.5±0.3 °C. The timeframe of gas exchanges recordings was about one minute each in a steady state condition. The Instantaneous Water Use Efficiency (W_t) was calculated as the ratio between Photosynthetic Assimilation (A) and Transpiration (E). The morphological parameters (area, perimeter and length) of the leaves used for gas-exchange analyses were measured with a Sky Leaf instrument, version 1.11 (SKYE Instruments Ltd., UK). The Leaf Mass per Area (LMA) was calculated as ratio between leaf dry mass and the corresponding leaf area.

2.3 Stable carbon isotopes

Ten leaves per clone (each one from a plant replicate) and per canopy layer were collected and used for analysis of stable carbon isotopes. At the end of the growing season the plant stems were cut in three sections (top, middle, and bottom) and 20 cm-long samples of wood at the base of each one were entirely ground by a blade mortar and used for isotope analyses. Fifteen mg of leaf or wood material were dried in a stove at 50 °C. The analysis of ¹³C/¹²C isotope ratios was performed by CF-IRMS (Isoprime GV, Elementar UK Ltd, UK) coupled with an elemental analyzer NA1500 (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy). The isotope ratio was expressed as ‰ referred to the international standard V-PDB (Vienna-Pee Dee Belemnite) according to the formula:

$$\delta = [(R_s - R_{std}) / R_{std}] * 1000$$

where R_s is the isotope ratio of the sample, R_{std} is the isotope ratio of the international standard and δ indicates the isotopic composition of carbon.

2.4 Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed with Systat 13 software package (Systat software, Chicago, IL) on 10 replicates (clonal plants) per each clone and per canopy layer. The significance of the variation between clones and canopy layers was tested by ANOVA, with Generalized Linear Model (GLM), because the distribution of data can be considered out of the normal range. Post-hoc tests (Fisher's Least Significant Difference) were performed to assess significant differences between samples. All statistical tests were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

Linear regression was applied on the whole dataset to test the correlation between pairwise combinations of leaf traits and carbon isotope data. In order to test the linear regression between leaf (monthly samplings) and stem carbon isotope data (one sampling at the end of season), the monthly leaf carbon isotope data were averaged across the growing season. The linear regression test was applied on the separate datasets of canopy layers and clones as well as on the combined dataset.

3. Results

3.1. Leaf morphology

Most leaf traits analyzed showed significant differences between the two clones, as well as across vertical canopy layers (Tab. 2). The leaf morphological parameters indicated bigger leaf size in the northern clone 58-861, when compared to the southern one Poli (Fig. 1b, c, and d), but the Leaf Mass per Area (LMA) was not significantly different between clones in all canopy layers (Fig. 1a). The leaf parameters showed a similar vertical profile in both clones, with leaves of bottom layer being significantly smaller than leaves of upper and intermediate layer. A different vertical profile was observed only in leaf perimeter of clone Poli, where the middle layer was intermediate between the upper and lower one (Fig. 1a).

3.2. Leaf gas exchange

In all canopy layers, the photosynthetic assimilation (A) was not significantly different between the clones (Fig. 2a). Furthermore, the vertical pattern of this trait was similar in both clones, with decreasing values from top to bottom and significant difference between top leaves and the lower layers. Leaf transpiration (E) was significantly higher in clone Poli than in 58-861, except at the top layer. Leaf transpiration of clone Poli was constant across the vertical profile, whereas in clone 58-861 it significantly decreased between top leaves and the lower layers (Fig. 2b). The stomatal conductance (g_s) significantly diverged between the clones in layers 2 and 3, and showed an opposite vertical profile but the differences across canopy layers were not significant (Fig. 2c). W_t was significantly higher in clone 58-861 and consistently decreased from top to bottom canopy in both clones (Fig. 2d).

3.3. Stable carbon isotopes

Leaf $\delta^{13}C$ showed significant differences between clones (Fig. 2e), and was more negative in clone Poli than in 58-861 in all canopy layers. However, the two clones showed a similar vertical profile of this trait, with top leaves being significantly different from the lower canopy layers.

The mean values of $\delta^{13}C$ of stem sections, sampled at the end of season, were less negative than leaf $\delta^{13}C$ of the respective canopy layer. Contrary to leaves, the vertical variation of stem wood $\delta^{13}C$ was not similar between the two clones, with only clone

Poli showing a significant difference between the top section and the lower stem (Fig. 2f).

3.4 Relationship between morphological and functional traits of leaves

The pairwise correlation among different leaf traits showed interesting relationships (Tab. 2). W_t was significantly correlated to leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ($R^2 = 0.72$). A strong correlation was found between morphological traits (perimeter, length, area) and leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Tab. 2). Furthermore, a strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.85$) was found between W_t and leaf area.

Stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was significantly correlated to leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (seasonal mean) from the same canopy layer if analyzing the combined data set from the two clones but this relationship was not significant in the separate data set of each clone (Tab. 3 and Supplementary data S1). The analysis on the whole canopy (combined dataset of all layers) revealed a stronger correlation in clone Poli ($R^2 = 0.79^*$) than in 58-861 ($R^2 = 0.44$ ns). A very strong and robust relationship ($R^2 = 0.89$, $p < 0.001$) between stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was highlighted by the linear regression test on the whole data set combining the three canopy layers and the two clones.

4. Discussion

Genotypic difference and vertical pattern of leaf traits

This study explored the intra-specific and intra-canopy variation of morphological and functional leaf traits by comparing two genetically divergent *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. The intra-specific variation in leaf traits observed in this study is relevant to predict the growth capacity and the environmental adaptation of these clones and confirms their divergent ecophysiological behavior reported in previous studies (Cocozza et al., 2010; Regier et al., 2009; Russo et al., 2014, 2016). Most leaf traits analyzed showed significant differences between the two clones, as well as across vertical canopy layers (Tab. 1). In the case of leaf area, stomatal conductance and stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, there was a significant difference between clones, but not across canopy profiles (Fig. 1a). Although the leaf size and functionality was markedly different between the two clones, the vertical pattern of leaf morphology parameters varied in a similar way. For most of these leaf traits the bottom layer was significantly different from the top layer. This pattern could be related to the vertical gradient of light radiation and to the formation of sun leaves in the upper canopy. In fact, solar radiation is highly variable in

a plantation (Casella and Ceulemans, 2002) and has a stronger impact on the leaf morphology in the upper canopy layers than in the lower ones (Hansen, 1991; Niinemets et al., 2004). By developing larger size, upper canopy leaves can take more advantage of high solar irradiation, than lower canopy leaves.

LMA and relationships with other traits

LMA is a composite variable of leaf thickness and leaf density and is functionally related to photosynthetic and respiratory rates (De La Riva et al., 2016). In this study, LMA was a plastic trait, which significantly varied both between clones and across canopy layers (Tab. 2). LMA usually increases from bottom to top canopy, driven by the vertical light gradient (Al Afas et al., 2007; Coble et al., 2014). We observed a similar vertical pattern in *P. nigra*, with LMA that increased from bottom to top canopy, consistently with the vertical gradient of PAR. However, the vertical fold-change of LMA was relatively small (range 100 to 110 g m⁻²), when compared to similar studies on young *Populus balsamifera* plants (70 to 100 g m⁻² reported by Soolanayakanahally et al. 2009; 20 to 50 g·m⁻², reported by Milla-Moreno et al. (2016). The small fold-change of LMA observed in this study is likely related to the small vertical variation of light across the canopy of young *P. nigra* plants.

LMA is known to be strongly associated with photosynthesis, leaf nitrogen content and mesophyll conductance (Niinemets, 1997; Milla-Moreno et al., 2016). However, we did not find significant correlation between LMA and other leaf traits (Tab. 3). Previous studies on young plants of *Populus angustifolia* (Kaluthota et al., 2015) and *P. balsamifera* (Soolanayakanahally et al., 2009) found significant correlation of LMA with A, leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and wood $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, although the R² coefficient was always lower than 0.5, as in our study. These literature reports, together with our results, suggest the absence of a tight functional relationship between LMA and other leaf traits in young *Populus* plants. On the opposite, LMA tightly correlated (R²>0.8) with W_t, V_{cmax}, and J_{max} in forest trees of *Fagus sylvatica* (Scartazza et al., 2016) and with leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in forest trees of *Acer sacharum* (Coble, 2015). In this study, the young age of the plants and the small variation of LMA could explain the lack of significant correlation with leaf traits. The relationships between leaf functional traits could be further investigated in natural

stands of mature *P. nigra* plants, where a wider gradient of environmental conditions could induce a larger plastic variation of leaf structure and functions.

Variation of leaf functional traits

In both *P. nigra* clones the photosynthetic assimilation significantly decreased from top to bottom, according to the expectation that PAR intensity drives photosynthesis across the canopy (Lalic et al., 2013). On the opposite, photosynthetic assimilation was not significantly different between the two *P. nigra* clones, despite differences between clones were observed in stomatal conductance and transpiration. The two clones shared a similar vertical profile of W_t , but clone 58-861 was consistently more water efficient than Poli across all the canopy layers. The difference in W_t between clones was driven by their divergent profile of stomatal conductance, rather than by difference in assimilation. The higher water use efficiency of clone 58-861 is consistent with the previous studies carried out on the same clones (Cocozza et al., 2010; Regier et al., 2009). We found a significant correlation between leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and W_t (Tab. 3), which confirms the suitability of carbon stable isotopes to estimate water use efficiency in *P. nigra*.

Stable carbon isotopes

The intrinsic water use efficiency was estimated by analysis of stable isotopes of carbon in vertical canopy layers. Less negative $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were observed in clone 58-861 than in the clone Poli across all layers (Fig. 1c). These results, together with leaf gas exchange (W_t), confirm the higher water use efficiency of clone 58-861 relative to Poli. The two *P. nigra* clones shared a similar vertical profile of leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, with increasing values from bottom to top canopy (acropetal enrichment). Such a vertical trend was reflected in stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of clone Poli, but not in clone 58-861. The difference in plant size and canopy architecture between the two clones could explain their vertical profile of stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Ogée et al., 2009). Clone 58-861 expresses specific canopy architecture, with bigger plant size, larger leaves and less dense branching than Poli. Such differences could involve a variable degree of lignification between the clones and contribute to their vertical profile of stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$.

In this study, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of stem sections was less negative (^{13}C enrichment) than leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the corresponding canopy layer, with more robust evidence in clone Poli. This observation in young *P. nigra* trees confirms similar data obtained in mature *F. silvatica* trees (Damesin and Lelarge, 2003; Scartazza et al., 2004). The carbon isotope enrichment between leaves and stem is generally caused by fractionation processes from source to sink (Peuke et al., 2006). It is also related to the different chemical composition (Brugnoli and Farquhar, 2000), with wood richer in lignin and structural carbohydrates and leaves richer in soluble carbohydrates and starch. These processes lead to an enrichment of ^{13}C in heterotrophic tissues when compared to leaves (Gessler et al., 2009; Loader et al. 2003) and could explain the ^{13}C enrichment between leaves and stem of *P. nigra*. At the end of the vegetation period, carbon transport from leaves into reserve pools, as well as allocation of stored assimilates within a tree can contribute to ^{13}C enrichment in stem (Voronin et al., 2012). In our experimental conditions, with two year old plants, the isotope composition of leaf tissues can be mostly related to short-term assimilation, with little turnover of older storage metabolites that could enrich the leaf carbon isotope signal.

Both *P. nigra* clones showed a similar vertical gradient of leaf and stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, with acropetal enrichment. The high values of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in top leaves reflects the higher photosynthetic capacity of sun-exposed leaves (Scartazza et al., 2016), consistently with the high assimilation and LMA observed in top canopy. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of stem represents an indicator of seasonal water use efficiency (Michelot et al., 2011), but there is little information about the vertical variation of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in tree stems. Some studies showed no vertical gradient across trunk sections (Gessler et al., 2014), whereas Voltas et al. (2013) reported a basipetal enrichment of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in stems of mature *Pinus sylvestris* L. trees. The basipetal ^{13}C enrichment is commonly associated to phloem transport and mobilization of storage carbon, but uncoupled with processes at leaf level (Gessler 2009). On the contrary, our study shows acropetal ^{13}C enrichment in stems of young *P. nigra* plants, suggesting a coupling between leaf and stem of the same canopy layer. In the first years of growth, this vertical profile is likely driven by leaf processes, without significant effect of storage tissues and assimilates from previous years.

We found a robust functional relationship between the seasonal mean of leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, which represents a novelty about the vertical variation of canopy functionality. By pooling data from the two clones, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of stem explained 89% of the

variance in leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (Tab. 4). This functional relationship between leaf and stem carbon pool indicates that assimilates are directly incorporated in stem tissues during the growing season (Helle and Schleser, 2004). The strong correlation between leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, obtained from pooled data of both clones, suggests the existence of a general functional relationship. When analyzing the result of each clone, a significant relationship was found in clone Poli only. This suggests that the small-sized plants of this clone transfer carbon between leaves and stem by short distance phloem transport (Voltas et al 2013).

Conclusions

In this study we obtained information about the canopy effect in young *P. nigra*, when grown in field conditions. These results are relevant for ecophysiology of poplar plantations and fill a gap of knowledge between forest ecosystems and small scale experiments in controlled environment. The short duration of our study, which spanned the first two years of plant life cycle, allows an easy interpretation of the functional relationships between leaf and stem carbon because of the small inter-conversion or inter-annual effect due to storage mobilization and metabolite turnover. The results indicate where, in the canopy, the substrate for stem growth is being sourced from. The overall functional relationship between leaf and stem carbon isotopes suggests a process of carbon allocation that favors a source-sink transport of assimilates within the same canopy layer. Such a process varies between the clones and likely depends on plant architecture and canopy size. Once validated by further evidence, this correlation could be useful in models that use stem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ as a predictor or proxy of leaf $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in ecophysiology studies on young trees.

Funding

This study was carried out with financial support from the European Commission, NOVELTREE project (FP7- KBBE Project ID 211868).

Bibliography

- Al Afas, N., Marron N., Ceulemans, R., 2007. Variability in *Populus* leaf anatomy and morphology in relation to canopy position, biomass production and varietal taxon. *Annals of Forest Science* 64, 521-532.
- Brugnoli, E., Farquhar, G.D., 2000. Photosynthetic fractionation of carbon isotopes. In: Leegood RC, Sharley TD, Von Cammerer S (eds). *Advances in photosynthesis: physiology and metabolism* (Kluwer, The Netherlands) 9, 399-434.
- Casella, E., Ceulemans, R., 2002. Spatial distribution of leaf morphology and physiological characteristics in relation to local radiation regime within canopies of 3-year-old *Populus* clones in coppice culture. *Tree Physiology* 22, 1277-1288.
- Chamaillard, S., Fichot, R., Vincent-Barbaroux, C., Bastien, C., Depierreux, C., Dreyer, E., Villar, M., Brignolas, F., 2011. Variations in bulk leaf carbon isotope discrimination, growth and related leaf traits among three *Populus nigra* L. populations. *Tree Physiology* 31, 1076–1087.
- Coble, A.P., 2015. Investigating within-canopy variation of functional traits and cellular structure of sugar maple (*Acer saccharum*) leaves. PhD Dissertation, Michigan Technological University.
- Coble, A.P., Cavaleri, M.A., Niinemets Ü., 2014. Light drives vertical gradients of leaf morphology in a sugar maple (*Acer saccharum*) forest. *Tree Physiology* 34, 146–158.
- Damesin, C., Lelarge, C., 2003. Carbon isotope composition of current-year shoots from *Fagus sylvatica* in relation to growth, respiration and use of reserves. *Plant, Cell Environment* 26, 207-219.
- De La Riva, E.G., Olmo, M., Poorter, H., Ubers, J.L., Villar, R., 2016. Leaf Mass per Area (LMA) and its relationship with leaf structure and anatomy in 34 Mediterranean woody species along a water availability gradient. *PLOS ONE* 11(2): e0148788. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0148788>.
- Farquhar, G.D., Ehleringer, J.R., Hubick, K.T., 1989. Carbon isotope discrimination and photosynthesis. *Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology* 40, 503–537, doi:10.1146/annurev.pp.40.060189.002443
- Gaudet, M., Pietrini, F., Beritognolo, I., Iori, V., Zacchini, M., Massacci, A., Mugnozza, G.S., Sabatti, M., 2011. Intraspecific variation of physiological and molecular response to cadmium stress in *Populus nigra* L. *Tree Physiology* 31, 1309–1318.
- Gessler, A., Brandes, E., Buchmann, N., Helle, G., Rennenberg, H., Barnard, R., 2009. Tracing carbon and oxygen isotope signals from newly assimilated sugars in the leaves to the tree ring archive. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 32, 780-795.
- Gessler, A., Ferrio, J.P., Hommel, R., Treydte, K., Werner, R.A., Monson, R.K., 2014. Stable isotopes in tree rings: towards a mechanistic understanding of isotope fractionation and mixing processes from leaves to wood. *Tree Physiology* 34, 796-818.
- Hansen, E.A., 1991. Poplar woody biomass yields: a look to the future. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 1, 1-7.
- Helle, G., Schleser, G.H., 2004. Beyond CO₂ fixation by Rubisco – an interpretation of C-13/C-12 variations in tree rings from novel intra-seasonal studies on broad-leaf trees. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 27, 367-380.

- Iori, V., Gaudet, M., Fabbrini, F., Pietrini, F., Beritognolo, I., Zaina, G., Mugnozza, G.S., Zacchini, M., Massacci, A., Sabatti, M., 2016. Physiology and genetic architecture of traits associated with cadmium tolerance and accumulation in *Populus nigra* L. *Trees* 30, 125–139.
- Jansson, S., Douglas, C.J., 2007. *Populus*: a model system for plant biology. *Annual Review for Plant Biology* 58, 435-458.
- Kaluthota, S., Pearce, D.W., Evans, L.M., Letts, M.G., Whitham, T.G., Rood, S.B., 2015. Higher photosynthetic capacity from higher latitude: foliar characteristics and gas exchange of southern, central and northern populations of *Populus angustifolia*. *Tree Physiology* 35(9), 936-948, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/tpv069>.
- Lalic, B., Firanj, A., Mihailovic, D.T., Podrascanin, Z. 2013. Parameterization of PAR vertical profile within horizontally uniform forest canopies for use in environmental modeling, *Journal of Geophysical Research Atmosphere* 118(15), 8156–8165, doi:10.1002/jgrd.50626.
- Loader N.J., Robertson I., McCarroll D., 2003. Comparison of stable carbon isotope ratios in the whole wood, cellulose and lignin of oak tree-rings. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 196, 395-407.
- Marmioli, M., Imperiale, D., Maestri, E., Marmioli, N., 2013. The response of *Populus* spp. to cadmium stress: chemical, morphological and proteomics study. *Chemosphere* 93, 1333-1344.
- Michelot, A., Eglin, T., Dufrene, E., Lelarge-Trouverie, C., Damesin, C., 2011. Comparison of seasonal variations in water-use efficiency calculated from the carbon isotope composition of tree rings and flux data in a temperate forest. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 34, 230-244.
- Milla-Moreno, E.A., McKown, A.D., Guy, R.D., Soolanayakanahally, R.Y., 2016. Leaf mass per area predicts palisade structural properties linked to mesophyll conductance in balsam poplar (*Populus balsamifera* L.). *Botany* 94, 225–239.
- Niinemets, Ü., Al Afas, N., Cescatti, A., Pellis, A., Ceulemans, R., 2004. Petiole length and biomass investment in support to modify light interception efficiency in dense poplar plantations. *Tree Physiology* 24, 141-154.
- Ogé J., Barbour M.M., Wingate L., Bert D., Bosc A., Stievenard M., Lambrot C., Pierre M., Bariac T., Loustau D., Dewar D.C., 2009. A single-substrate model to interpret intra-annual stable isotope signals in tree-ring cellulose. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 32: 1071-1090.
- Peuke, A.D., Gessler, A., Rennenberg, H., 2006. The effect of drought on C and N stable isotopes in different fractions of leaves, stems and roots of sensitive and tolerant beech ecotypes. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 29(5), 823-35.
- Pliura, A., Suchockas, V., Sarsekova, D., Gudynaitė, V., 2014. Genotypic variation and heritability of growth and adaptive traits, and adaptation of young poplar hybrids at northern margins of natural distribution of *Populus nigra* in Europe. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 70, 513–529.
- Regier, N., Streb, S., Coccozza, C., Schaub, M., Cherubini, P., Zeeman, S.C., Frey, B., 2009. Drought tolerance of two black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.) clones: contribution of carbohydrates and oxidative stress defence. *Plant, Cell & Environment* 32, 1724-1736.

- Russo, G., Sabatti, M., De Angelis, P., 2016. Study of short-term plasticity in two contrasting genotypes of *Populus nigra* L. *Journal of Plant Physiology* 200, 1-6, doi: 10.1016/j.jplph.2016.05.006.
- Russo, G., De Angelis, P., Mickle, J., Barone Lumaga, M.R., 2014. Stomata morphological traits in two different genotypes of *Populus nigra* L. *I-Forest – Biogeosciences and Forestry*, doi: 10/3832/ifor1104-007.
- Scartazza, A., Mata, C., Matteucci, G., Yakir, D., Moscatello, S., Brugnoli, E., 2004. Comparisons of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of photosynthetic products and ecosystem respiratory CO_2 and their responses to seasonal climate variability. *Oecologia* 140, 340-351.
- Scartazza, A., Di Baccio, D., Bertolotto, P., Gavrichkova, O., Matteucci, G., 2016. Investigating the European beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) leaf characteristics along the vertical canopy profile: leaf structure, photosynthetic capacity, light energy dissipation and photoprotection mechanisms, *Tree Physiology* 36, 1060-1076, doi: 10.1093/treephys/tpw038.
- Smulders, M.J.M., Cottrell, J.E., Lefèvre, F., van der Schoot, J., Arens, P., Vosman, B., Tabbener, H.E., (...), Boerjan, W. 2008. Structure of the genetic diversity in black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.) populations across European river systems: Consequences for conservation and restoration. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 255 (5-6), pp. 1388-1399. doi: 10.1016/j.foreco.2007.10.063.
- Soolanayakanahally, R.Y., Guy, R.D., Street N.R., Robinson K.M., Silim, S.N., Albrechtsen, B.R., Jansson, S., 2015. Comparative physiology of allopatric *Populus* species: geographic clines in photosynthesis, height growth, and carbon isotope discrimination in common gardens. *Frontiers in Plant Sciences* 6:528, doi: 10.3389/fpls.2015.00528.
- Van Der Merwe, N., Medina, E., 1991. The canopy effect, carbon isotopic ratios and foodwebs in Amazonia. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 18(3), 249-259.
- Voltas, J., Camarero, J.J., Carulla, D., Aguilera, M., Ortiz, A., Ferrio, J.P. A retrospective, dual-isotope approach reveals individual predispositions to winter-drought induced tree dieback in the southernmost distribution limit of Scots pine. *Plant, Cell and Environment* 36, 1435-1448.
- Voronin, V., Ivlev, A.A., Oskolkov, P., Boettger, T., 2012. Intra-seasonal dynamics in metabolic processes of $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ and $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$ in components of Scots pine twigs from southern Siberia interpreted with a conceptual framework based on the Carbon Metabolism Oscillatory Model. *BMC Plant Biology* 12:76. doi:10.1186/1471-2229-12-76.
- Zacchini, M., Pietrini, F., Scarascia Mugnozza, G., Iori, V., Pietrosanti, L., Massacci, A., 2009. Metal tolerance, accumulation and translocation in poplar and willow clones treated with cadmium in hydroponics. *Water Air & Soil Pollution* 197, 23-34.

Tab. 1. Seasonal mean (\pm st. dev.) of the photosynthetic active radiation (PAR) measured at different vertical canopy layers in two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. Average of three minimum measurements around the leaves not subjected to wind and flutter.

Clone	Layer	PAR ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Poli	Top	1329.7 \pm 5
	Middle	974.9 \pm 11
	Bottom	641.3 \pm 19
58-861	Top	1286.7 \pm 9
	Middle	918.6 \pm 15
	Bottom	509.3 \pm 22

Tab. 2. Statistical significance of the effect of clone and canopy layer after ANOVA of leaf traits and stable carbon isotopes in two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. Each sample included leaves collected from ten replicated plants per clone and per canopy layer. Significance code, ***= $P \leq 0.001$; **= $P \leq 0.01$; *= $P \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant.

Trait	Clone	Canopy layer
LMA	*	**
Perimeter	***	***
Area	***	ns
Length	***	**
Assimilation (A)	ns	***
Transpiration (E)	***	*
Stomatal Conductance (g_s)	***	ns
Instantaneous WUE (W_t)	***	***
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ Leaf	***	**
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ Stem	***	ns

Tab. 3. Pearson correlation coefficient between pairs of morphological and physiological leaf traits analysed across canopy layers of two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. LMA, Leaf Mass per Area; A, photosynthetic assimilation; E, leaf transpiration; g_s , stomatal conductance; W_t , instantaneous Water Use Efficiency. Significance code, ***= $P \leq 0.001$; **= $P \leq 0.01$; *= $P \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant.

	LMA	Perimeter	Area	Length	A	E	g_s	W_t
LMA								
Perimeter	0.35							
Area	0.34	0.99***						
Length	0.32	0.99***	1.00***					
A	0.43	0.67*	0.71*	0.70*				
E	0.45	-0.01	0.01	-0.004	0.48			
g_s	0.15	-0.17	-0.16	-0.16	0.30	0.81***		
W_t	0.30	0.81***	0.85***	0.84***	0.91***	0.08	-0.04	
$\delta^{13}C$ Leaf	0.44	0.77**	0.80***	0.78***	0.65	0.15	-0.04	0.72***

Tab. 4. Coefficient of determination (R^2) of linear regression between leaf (L) $\delta^{13}C$ (seasonal mean values) and the corresponding stem section (S) in three vertical canopy layers (L), (1 = top layer, 2 = middle layer, 3 = bottom layer) in two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. Linear regression analyses were performed on separate datasets of clone and layer and on the whole set of pooled data. Significance code, ***= $P \leq 0.001$; **= $P \leq 0.01$; *= $P \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant.

Clone	Stem sections	Canopy layers			
		L1	L2	L3	Whole canopy
	S1	0.12 ^{ns}			
Poli	S2		0.29 ^{ns}		0.79*
	S3			0.66 ^{ns}	
	S1	0.10 ^{ns}			
58-861	S2		0.53 ^{ns}		0.44 ^{ns}
	S3			0.01 ^{ns}	
	S1	0.59**			
All plants	S2		0.72**		0.89***
	S3			0.64**	

Fig. 1. Morphological traits of leaves analysed across canopy layers of two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. a)-Leaf Mass per Area (LMA); b) Area; c) Perimeter; d) Length. Each sample included leaves collected from ten replicated plants per clone and per canopy layer. Bars represent mean value \pm standard error. Canopy layers (1 to 3) are numbered top to bottom. Different letters indicate significant differences between canopy layers within data of each clone. Symbols over the bars represent significance of differences between clones. Significance code, ***= $P \leq 0.001$; **= $P \leq 0.01$; *= $P \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant.

Fig. 2. Physiological traits of leaves and stem wood analysed across canopy layers of two *P. nigra* clones grown in common garden. a) Photosynthetic assimilation; b) Transpiration; c) Stomatal conductance; d) Instantaneous Water Use Efficiency; e) Carbon stable isotopes of leaves; f) Carbon stable isotopes of stem. Each sample included leaves and stem sections collected from ten replicated plants per clone and per canopy layer. Bars represent mean value \pm standard error. Canopy layers (1 to 3) are numbered top to bottom. Different letters indicate significant differences between canopy layers within data of each clone. Symbols over the bars represent significance of differences between clones. Significance code, ***= $P \leq 0.001$; **= $P \leq 0.01$; *= $P \leq 0.05$; ns = not significant.